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Observations of Kelvin waves in tropical and subtropical regions using Radiosonde and AIRS Satellite Temperature data

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Abstract:	<p>Kelvin wave (KW) is a special type of gravity wave that is affected by the earth's rotation and trapped at the equator. It's played a crucial role in atmospheric dynamics and to better understanding in prediction of tropical cyclones and their behavior. In this study, we analyze atmospheric temperature perturbation profiles over troposphere lower stratosphere (TLS) (1 - 25 km) to investigate the effect of KW obtained from the RS and AIRS satellite data from March 2019 to February 2020 over tropical and subtropical region. The characteristics of KW were further investigated by fitting a sinusoidal approximation by assuming zonal wave number 1 and 2 to the AIRS temperature perturbations using nonlinear inversion algorithm. It is found that the periodicity of observed KW is about 10 - 13.8 days in Spring, 9 - 14 days in Summer, 10 - 14.5 days in Autumn, and 9.2 - 14 days in Winter with a vertical wavelength of 8.5 - 10 km, 3.8 - 12.5 km, 4 - 7.5 km, and 4.4 - 11 km respectively in tropical Addis's station. Similarly, the periodicity observed KW is about 8.8 - 13.3 days in Spring, 7.8 days in Summer, 7.5 - 13.3 days in Autumn, and 6.4 - 10 days in Winter with a vertical wavelength of 6 - 9.2 km, 7.8 - 11.2 km, 7.8 km, and 10 km respectively in subtropical Cairo station. One of the characteristics of KW in downward propagation of KW observed to be pronounced in summer season from both stations. The maximum amplitude of KW at the tropical station Addis is 8 K in Winter and for the subtropical station Cairo is level at 4 K in Winter, which supports exponentially decreases (decrement) of equatorial wave from the tropics to the subtropics. The maximum KW and gravity waves are observed in summer. The correlation of tropopause height with KW and gravity waves are 0.48 and 0.86 respectively. The cause of the large amplitude KW activity and its significant association with the tropical tropopause fluctuation may be below Outgoing longwave radiation (OLR) values, which are in turn linked to significant convective activity during the summer. OLR data shows that deep convection activity is developed over tropical and subtropical region during the KW events due to either driven by convectively coupled wave or free waves over tropical and subtropical regions, which is consistent with the previous results.</p>

To

The Editor

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19 July, 2024

From

Mr. Tsehaye

Research student,

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Respected Sir/Madam,

Sub: Submission of Manuscript related to Atmospheric Sciences “**Observations of Kelvin waves in tropical and subtropical regions using Radiosonde and AIRS Satellite Temperature data**”.

It gives me immense pleasure and fortune to publish my research work in your esteemed journal. I am here with enclosing manuscript entitled “**Observations of Kelvin waves in tropical and subtropical regions using Radiosonde and AIRS Satellite Temperature data**” for your kind perusal. Our article is first of its kind from Ethiopia country in applying different 2-D FFT techniques to quantify the tropopause oscillations at Tropospheric lower stratospheric region connecting tropical and subtropical climates, which are very less studied, our promising results are crucial for modelling and prediction of temperature in TLS region by National Meteorological Agency, Ethiopia. The content of the article clearly fits to Aims and Scope of the Journal (Atmospheric Sciences). The authors confirm that neither the manuscript nor any parts of its content are currently under consideration or published in another journal. Please consider our request on “**APC waivers for financial need**” as our country Ethiopia comes under “**world’s lowest income countries**” as defined by the World Bank. Moreover, first author of this journal is a research student, who is unemployed, he couldn’t pay APC charges. Hence please consider our request and wave for us further do the needful for its speedy publication in your esteemed journal. Thanking you for your assistance in this regard.

Yours Sincerely

Mr.Tsehaye

Highlights of the work:

- The main cause of tropopause variation in the tropical and subtropical region is Kelvin wave.
- The maximum kelvin wave and gravity waves are observed in summer.
- A kelvin wave with downward propagation was observed in the time height cross section of temperature fluctuations from both RS and AIRS data.
- The Cold point tropopause height (CPT_h) was seen to increase variation during March 12, March 15, June 15 - 17, October 11, October 13 and December 11 - 15.
- The maximum amplitude of kelvin wave at the tropical station Addis is 8 K and for the subtropical station Cairo is level at 4 K, which supports exponentially decreases (decrement) of kelvin wave from the tropics to the subtropics.

Observations of Kelvin waves in tropical and subtropical regions using Radiosonde and AIRS Satellite Temperature data

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ABSTRACT

Kelvin wave (KW) is a special type of gravity wave that is affected by the earth's rotation and trapped at the equator. It's play a crucial role in atmospheric dynamics (climate phenomena) and to better understanding in prediction of tropical cyclones and their behaviour. In this study, we analyze atmospheric temperature perturbation profiles over troposphere lower stratosphere (TLS) (1 - 25 km) to investigate the effect of equatorial kelvin wave obtained from the RS and AIRS satellite data from March 2019 to February 2020 over tropical and subtropical region. The characteristics of equatorial kelvin wave were further investigated by fitting a sinusoidal approximation by assuming zonal wave number 1 and 2 to the AIRS temperature perturbations using non linear inversion algorithm. It is found that the periodicity of observed equatorial kelvin wave is about 10 - 13.8 days in Spring, 9 - 14 days in Summer, 10 - 14.5 days in Autumn, and 9.2 - 14 days in Winter with a vertical wavelength of 8.5 - 10 km, 3.8 - 12.5 km, 4 - 7.5 km, and 4.4 - 11 km respectively in tropical Addis station. Similarly the periodicity observed equatorial kelvin wave is about 8.8 - 13.3 days in Spring, 7.8 days in Summer, 7.5 - 13.3 days in Autumn, and 6.4 - 10 days in Winter with a vertical wavelength of 6 - 9.2 km, 7.8 - 11.2 km, 7.8 km, and 10 km respectively in subtropical Cairo station. One of the characteristics of kelvin wave in downward propagation of kelvin wave observed to be pronounced in summer season from both stations. The maximum amplitude of equatorial kelvin wave at the tropical station Addis is 8 K in Winter and for the subtropical station Cairo is level at 4 K in Winter, which supports exponentially decreases (decrement) of equatorial wave from the tropics to the subtropics. The maximum equatorial kelvin wave and gravity waves are observed in summer. The correlation of tropopause height with equatorial kelvin wave and gravity waves are 0.48 and 0.86 respectively. The cause of the large amplitude kelvin wave activity and its significant association with the tropical tropopause fluctuation may be below Outgoing longwave radiation (OLR) values, which are in turn linked to significant convective activity during the summer. Outgoing longwave radiation (OLR) data shows that deep convection activity is developed over tropical and subtropical region during the KW events due to either driven by convectively coupled wave or free waves over tropical and subtropical regions, which is consistent with the previous results.

1. Introduction

Equatorial kelvin waves serve as the fundamental building blocks of many aspects of tropical weather and climate (Wheeler and Nguyen, 2015). They are geophysical fluid waves, existing for a range of spatial and temporal scales, which are trapped near the equator. They propagate in the zonal and vertical directions, and may exist at any altitude level in the atmosphere or depth in the ocean. They cause oscillations in the pressure, temperature, and winds or currents, with the magnitude of such oscillations being large enough to cause changes the weather. Equatorial waves are important for their organized contributions to tropical upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (UTLS) circulation, constituent transport, stratospheric dehydration and cloud formation processes. In the equatorial

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waves UTLS propagate vertically and provide important forcing for the stratospheric quasibiennial oscillation (QBO) and semiannual oscillation (SAO), and hence it is important to quantify wave behavior in observations and use measurements to evaluate and constrain models (Kawatani et al., 2009).

Atmospheric temperature variability in the tropics is coupled with dynamical and physical processes, which have a crucial impact on the Earth's climate. Variability in the tropical tropopause region is of special interest because it has an important role in troposphere – stratosphere coupling and exchange (Holton et al., 1995; Fueglistaler et al., 2009) and associated global radiation budget. Thus, detailed knowledge of dynamical processes in the tropical upper troposphere and lower stratosphere is essential for better understanding climate variability and change. It has been found, that decadal variations in global surface climate may be significantly influenced by changes in stratospheric water vapor (Solomon et al., 2010), which is controlled by temperatures near the tropical tropopause (Mote et al., 1996). Furthermore, vertically propagating equatorial waves, which originate from the troposphere and propagate into the upper atmosphere, are main drivers of global-scale zonal wind variation, which is called the quasi-biennial oscillation (QBO). The QBO manifests itself as alternating easterly and westerly zonal winds in the tropical stratosphere with a period of approximately 28 months. It has large impacts on the entire global atmosphere (Baldwin et al., 2001). Diabatic heating by organized tropical convection can excite atmospheric equatorial waves, which control the spatial and temporal distribution of convective heating (Dunkerton, 1989; Holton et al., 2001).

Equatorial atmospheric waves, including eastward propagating Kelvin waves, are generated by heating associated with convection (Garcia and Salby, 1987; Wheeler and Kiladis, 1999; Tsuda et al., 1994; Alexander and Pfister, 1995; Karoly et al., 1996; Vincent and Joan Alexander, 2000; Alexander and Tsuda, 2008). Atmospheric equatorial Kelvin waves were theorized by Matsuno (1966) and Holton and Lindzen (1968) and first observed by Wallace and Gousky (1968). Equatorial Kelvin waves can propagate vertically in regions of background easterly winds, while they become trapped below regions of westerly winds, and they exhibit strong interactions with the stratospheric QBO (Sato and Dunkerton, 1997). Equatorial Kelvin waves dominate sub-seasonal variability in the tropical tropopause region (Tindall et al., 2006). They modulate the height and temperature of the tropical tropopause (Tsuda et al., 1994; Shimizu and Tsuda, 1997) and were found to be important for cirrus formation (Boehm and Verlinde, 2000; Immler et al., 2008; Suzuki et al., 2013) and dehydration of air entering the lower stratosphere (Fujiwara et al., 2001). Furthermore, they play an important role in stratosphere–troposphere exchange of ozone (Fujiwara et al., 1998). Equatorial Kelvin waves in the lower stratosphere commonly occur with periods of order 10–20 days and are known as slow Kelvin waves or Wallace–Gousky waves (Wallace and Gousky, 1968; Maruyama, 1968). What is commonly referred to as fast waves with periods of 6–10 days in the stratosphere (Hirota, 1979) and the 3–6 day period ultra-fast waves in the stratosphere–mesosphere are now well-established (Salby et al., 1984; Canziani et al., 1995; Riggini et al., 1997).

Equatorial kelvin waves have been identified using radiosonde temperature and wind measurements (Wallace and Kousky, 1968; Tsuda et al., 1994; Holton et al., 2001). Due to the limited spatial coverage of the radiosonde network, observations were confined to a few specific locations. Radiosonde observations though have the advantage of high vertical resolution, but they lack global coverage particularly over oceanic regions. In order to study the global behaviour and horizontal propagation characteristics of these waves, satellite-based measurements are more useful because they offer global coverage (Hirota, 1979). Later, satellite temperature measurements provided a more global view on atmospheric dynamics. Equatorial atmospheric kelvin waves have been investigated using satellite data from Nimbus-7 LIMS (Limb Infrared Monitor of the Stratosphere) (Salby et al., 1984), the Microwave Limb Sounder (MLS) (Mote et al., 2002), and High Resolution Dynamics Limb Sounder (HIRDLS) (Alexander and Ortland, 2010). Furthermore, several studies on atmospheric Kelvin waves are based on analysis or reanalysis data from numerical weather prediction (NWP) centers (Suzuki et al., 2010; Fujiwara et al., 2012; Flannaghan and Fueglistaler, 2013). Kelvin waves have been identified in the troposphere lower stratosphere using COSMIC (Anthes et al., 2008; Cao et al., 2022; Brahmanandam et al., 2010; Randel and Wu, 2005; Das et al., 2022). Ofcourse literature search reveals null report on subtropical kelvin wave analysis, which motivates to take up this work. Moreover previous researchers concentrates on $5^{\circ}N$ - $5^{\circ}S$ belt of equatorial kelvin wave observations. We extended latitudinal belt for tropics 0 - $15^{\circ}N$ in addition to subtropical bands of 22 - $30^{\circ}N$. This work is first of its kind to observe kelvin wave analysis from subtropics using RS and AIRS satellite observations over a period of March 2019 - February 2020. The methodology and data availability are covered in section 2. Section 3 describes the outcome and the discussion. Part 4 describes the summary and conclusion.

2. Data and the Analysis Methods

2.1. Radiosonde data

Radiosondes are battery-powered telemetry instrument packages that are carried into the atmosphere typically by a weather balloon; they measure altitude, pressure, temperature, relative humidity and wind (both speed and direction) at high altitudes and transmit them by radio to a ground receiver. Radiosonde observations have been carried out daily at the Addis Ababa synoptic meteorological station since 1969. The radiosonde data from Addis Ababa synoptic meteorological station has undergone quality checks by Global Radiosonde Archive (IGRA) through scrutinizing presence of physically implausible values, climatological outliers, and temporal and vertical inconsistencies in temperature (Durre et al., 2006). In this study, we use high - resolution Radio sounding data at tropical Addis Ababa station and subtropical Cairo station covering the period from 2006 - 2020. Before blowing up, weather balloons usually raise for 90 minutes are fewer, covers a distance of 19 to 32 km. In Ethiopia and

Cairo station launched balloons burst after 25 km, the radiosonde data were accessed through CDAAC webpage (<https://rda.ucar.edu/datasets/ds351.0/>).

2.2. AIRS data

The Atmospheric Infrared Sounder (AIRS) instrument (Aumann et al., 2003; Chahine et al., 2006) is one of six instruments aboard NASA Aqua satellite, which has been operating in a nearly polar, low earth orbit (705 km altitude, 98.2 inclination, 100 min period) since May 2002. The observations provide nearly global coverage with 14.4 orbits per day in a sun - synchronous orbit. We use the version 6 standard Level 3 data from AIRS/AMSU combined retrievals (Susskind et al., 2014; Tian et al., 2013) on a daily timescale, taking the arithmetic mean from both ascending and descending nodes of the orbit when available. Data is analyzed with $1^0 \times 1^0$ grid horizontal resolution, centered on the half degree, which we then averaged to shift to the full degree. Data are available from March 2019 through February 2020. Data are analyzed on standard pressure levels (primarily 10, 70, and 100 hPa). Through the troposphere AIRS temperature retrievals have a vertical resolution of about 2 km (Susskind et al., 2014), however in the stratosphere the vertical resolution is not sufficiently known due to uncertainties in the weighing functions. Launched into Earth-orbit on May 4, 2002 aboard NASAs Aqua satellite, the Atmospheric Infrared Sounder, AIRS, provides data critical to the monitoring of Earths atmosphere. The AIRS on NASA's Aqua satellite, gathers infrared energy emitted from Earth's surface and atmosphere globally, every day. Its data provides 3D measurements of temperature and water vapor through the atmospheric column along with a host of trace gases, surface and cloud properties. AIRS data are used by weather prediction centers around the world to improve their forecasts. They are also used to assess the skill of climate models and in applications ranging from volcanic plume detection to drought forecasting. AIRS uses cutting edge infrared technology to create three-dimensional maps of air and surface temperature, water vapor, and cloud properties. With 2378 spectral channels, AIRS has a spectral resolution more than 100 times greater than previous infrared sounders and provides more accurate information on the vertical profiles of atmospheric temperature and moisture. AIRS can also measure trace greenhouse gases such as ozone, carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, and methane. AIRS temperature profiles have an accuracy in the troposphere that matches the accuracy achieved by radiosondes launched from ground stations.

2.3. Outgoing Longwave Radiation (OLR) data

The daily Outgoing Longwave Radiation (OLR) data is available in latitude-longitude grids from the AIRS satellite. This data measures the amount of terrestrial radiation released into space and provides insights into cloud cover and water vapor in the atmosphere. The record spans from 1979 to the present and is primarily derived from high-resolution infrared radiation sounder (HIRS) observations, as well as data from newer infrared hyperspectral sounders like the Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer (IASI) and the Cross-track Infrared Sounder (CrIS). In this study we

take the OLR data available with the NOAA earth system research laboratory under physical sciences division, averaged over 22 - 35° N and 0 - 15° N from March 2019 to February 2020. It should be noted that the daily OLR data are available 2.5° x 2.5° latitude - longitude grid, with data gaps filled by linear interpolation to provide complete sampling. When OLR values are low, it indicates strong convection associated with cyclones.

2.4. Methods of Analysis

2.4.1. Fast Fourier transform Analysis

Fast Fourier transform (FFT) is the most commonly used method for estimating frequency spectra of evenly sampled data (Cooley and Tukey, 1965). It enables the approximation of a time series sampled from a continuous distribution over discrete time steps, through a series of complex sine and cosine waves with varying frequencies. The expected Fourier transform of a discretized signal is given by the convolution of the true transform and the transform of a Dirac comb window function designating those measurement times (VanderPlas, 2018). We applied 2-D FFT analysis technique to identify the periodicity of upper tropospheric lower stratospheric Kelvin wave oscillations by using RS and AIRS temperature data in Addis and Cairo station. In this study, we have used the space-time spectral analysis method, two-dimensional fast Fourier transform (2D-FFT) (Hayashi, 1982), to extract Kelvin wave components from the temperature profiles provided by the AIRS. Interested readers may refer the theory of 2 D FFT technique by (Babu and Stoica, 2010; Munteanu et al., 2016).

2.4.2. Curve Fitting

Equatorial Kelvin waves have the strongest amplitudes at the equator with zonal wave number 1 and 2 predominant (Mote et al., 2002). To isolate dominant wave numbers, a fitting function,

$$T(\lambda, d) = \sum_{i=1}^2 [A_i \sin(\omega_i(\lambda - p_i))] \quad (1)$$

where $\omega_i = \frac{2\pi i}{P}$, λ is longitude, p_i is the phase of wave, P is periodicity of the wave, $T(\lambda, d)$ is temperature in a function of longitude and days, A_i is the amplitude of the wave. Mixing with wave 1 and wave 2 components is then applied to best fit the temperature fluctuations of T' data with the amplitude A and phase p for all longitudes λ solved by means of a nonlinear least-square method. Figure 1 (b) shows a sinusoidal fit with 198 - 200 K peak-to-peak oscillation derived from the atmospheric temperature (T) data at 17 km altitude in the equatorial region during 10 June, 2019. The background temperature profile T_o (fitted model temperature) curve reveals a mixed wave with wave 1 and wave 2 components. When this data processing is carried out over a longer span of time, the time evolution of large scale zonal waves propagation is revealed. Figure 1 (a - h) illustrates the application of T and fitted T_o to a time series at altitudes of 15 km, 17 km, and 25 km from March 2019 to February 2020.

2.4.3. Kelvin Wave Identification Procedure

The atmospheric temperature profile is believed to be composed of the background and fluctuating temperature profiles due to different oscillation mode waves such as kelvin waves. Identifying the characteristics of kelvin waves from the temperature profiles requires removing the background temperature profile. Sinusoidal fitting has been usually applied to estimate the background temperature profiles (Mote et al., 2002). In the present study, the background temperature profile variations are estimated by sinusoidal fitting explained by (Tsuda et al., 1994), and hence the temperature profiles are estimated by subtracting the background quantity from the original measurements. The following procedure has been adopted to extract kelvin wave characteristics in the AIRS temperature profiles. In the first step, the temperature data has been interpolated to 0.5 km. It is to be noted that the original AIRS data are available at 1 km vertical resolution and have an effective vertical resolution on the order of 1.5 km or above in the UTLS and stratospheric region. Due to the high inclination 98.2 orbit of AIRS satellites, the temperature profiles data occurrence rates around the equator are rather sparse and hence an interpolation method in longitude has been applied on the temperature profile data to fill-in the missing data starting from ground to 30 km altitudes. Figure 1 depicted in previous section displays the longitudinal temperature profile (blue circles) at 17 km on 10 March 2019, on 10 June 2019, on 10 September 2019 and on 10 December 2019 over the entire equatorial region super imposed by sinusoidal fit (red solid circles). In the second step, we use a sinusoidal T_o to best fit to the interpolated data, which is considered to be background temperature (model temperature T) variation.

The background values were then removed from each temperature profile corresponding to each altitude and the resulting fluctuation ($T' = T - T_o$) data has been utilized to identify the Kelvin wave features. Furthermore, fluctuation data during every three month (season) period are put together as ensembles to show the seasonal variation of Kelvin wave activity for Spring (March, April and May (MAM)), summer (Jun, July and August (JJA)), Autumn or Fall (September, October and November (SON)) and winter (December, January and February (DJF)) of March 2019 to February 2020. As a final step, we applied a 2-D Fast Fourier Transform (2D-FFT) on large scale temperature fluctuation components and the subsequent application of incoherent integration on the output of the FFT to identify the typical characteristics of Kelvin waves. The vertical wavelengths (λ_z in the z axis) estimated from simple wave theory for kelvin waves (Holton et al., 2001):

$$\lambda_z = \frac{2\pi}{N} \left(\frac{\lambda_x}{\tau} - \bar{U} \right) \quad (2)$$

Where, \bar{U} , N , τ , λ_x , and λ_z are velocity of mean zonal wind, bouyancy frequency, wave period (observed parameter), zonal wavelength, and vertical wavelength (observed parameter) respectively. N is approximately equal to 0.02 s^{-1} (Holton et al., 2001), zonal wavelength λ_x for wave number 1 is equivalent to 40,200 km, which is the circumference

of the earth's mean radius plus height from the surface, for wave number 2, λ_x is equivalent to 20,100 km and \bar{U} is variant by time and altitude depending on the quasi-biennial oscillation (QBO). According to monthly mean zonal wind data at Singapore, \bar{U} is approximately equal to -1.73 m/s, -1.63 m/s, 0.13 m/s, and 0.88 m/s during Spring, Summer, Autumn, and Winter respectively, where the minus sign indicates easterly.

2.4.4. Gravity wave Energy

We have calculated the wave kinetic energy using fluctuation of zonal and meridional wind observed by radiosonde using equation (3) and also potential energy from RS temperature fluctuation data by applying equation (4) (Ratnam et al., 2006), integrated over the heights of 15 – 25 km. The linear correlation between kinetic and potential energy was particularly significant (0.716). Gravity Wave (GW) activity is estimated by calculating the potential (E_p), kinetic (E_k) and total (E_T) energies per unit mass as defined by:

$$E_k = \frac{1}{2}(u'^2 + v'^2) \quad (3)$$

$$E_p = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{g}{N} \frac{T'}{T} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where $g(z)$ is the acceleration due to gravity. $N(z)$ is the oscillation frequency of the parcel of the atmosphere (usually called Buoyancy or Brunt–vaisala frequency) and it is expressed as

$$N^2 = \frac{g}{T} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} + \Gamma_d \right) \quad (5)$$

where $\Gamma_d = \frac{g}{c_p}$ is adiabatic lapse rate, c_p is the specific heat capacity at constant pressure of the atmosphere and for this study 9.8×10^{-3} (K/m) lapse rate is adopted.

$$E_T = E_k + E_p \quad (6)$$

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Longitude - Time investigation of kelvin wave in the TLS region over tropical and subtropical regions

Our aim is to investigate prevailing of kelvin waves at 15 km (corresponds to tropopause of subtropical region), 17 km (corresponds to tropopause of tropical region) and 25 km (lower stratosphere) for tropical and subtropical regions. Procedure of identification of kelvin wave has been explained in section 2.4.3. First we ensemble the temperature fluctuations at the pressure level of 100 hPa (15 km) for subtropical region during every three months i.e seasonal

variations of kelvin wave activity for four seasons has been calculated and corresponding longitude - time contours are draw for each season (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (C), Autumn and (d) Winter in Figure 2. The temperature minimum in the cold region varies episodically during these months (in response to variations in deep convection), but overall the patterns are quasi-stationary. The maximum amplitude of kelvin wave from Figure 2 (a - d) in spring, Summer, Autumn and Winter are 3 K, 4 K, 4 K and 4 K respectively. In spring the kelvin wave (here after KW) propagets in all longitude in the month of April 16 to May 31 (in the day of 45 to 92). From Figure 2 (b) the KW increase slightly in the month of August 20 - 30. The periodicity of KW in June is 5 days, in July is 20 days and in August is 15 days. In Autumn KW have seen in the end of October and the beginning of November. The periodicity of KW in Autumn and Winter are 10 and 5 days respectively.

Figure 3 (a - d) depicts the longitude time contours of temperature fluctuations at 15 km (100 hPa pressure level) for tropical station Addis during March 2019 to February 2020. The maximum amplitude of KW in tropical region from Figure 3 (a - d) in spring, Summer, Autumn and Winter are 7 K, 6 K, 7 K and 8 K respectively. The periodicity of KW observed in Spring, Summer, Autumn, and Winter are 10 days, 20 days, 12 days, and 7 days respectively. The temperature fluctuations from March 2019 to February 2020 at 15 km are characterized by the known climatological structure of cold temperatures over longitudes $180^{\circ}W - 50^{\circ}E$ in spring, $50^{\circ}W - 50^{\circ}E$ in summer, $(140^{\circ}-50^{\circ}) W - (50^{\circ}-140^{\circ}) E$ in Autumn, and $100^{\circ}W - 40^{\circ}E$ in winter associated with maximum convection (Randel and Wu, 2005; Highwood and Hoskins, 1998; Hormann and Brandt, 2009; Seidel et al., 2001). The temperature minimum in the cold region varies episodically during march 3 - 10, Jun 15 - 23, October 15 - 25 and January 3 (in response to variations in deep convection), but overall the patterns are quasi-stationary. In contrast, temperature fluctuations at 15 km show zonal wavenumber-1 structure with regular eastward propagation. These observational results are consistent with earlier reported results including (Garcia and Salby, 1987; Randel and Wu, 2005). Randel and Wu (2005) using CHAMP and SAC-C RO data have found the quasi-stationary wave structures near the tropopause (15 km) for four consecutive months starting from March 2019 to February 2020. The periodicity of KW at 15 km in tropical station for the four seasons are 15 days.

We generalize Figure 2 (subtropical region) and Figure 3 (tropical region) the maximum amplitude observed 4 K (Summer, Autumn and Winter) in subtropical region and 8 K (Winter) in subtropical region which is KW more fluctuate in the tropical region and our results are match with the theory of KW is maximum amplitude in the equator and exponentially decay away from the equator. The maximum periodicity in the subtropical region is 13.3 day in summer and the maximum periodicity observed in tropical region is 20 day which is periodicity and amplitude have no any connections. The maximum tropopause height in the tropical region observed due to KW is maximum temperature fluctuation (maximum amplitude) in the equator.

Now, we try to analyze KW fluctuation at 17 km correspond to tropical tropopause. Figure 4 (a - b) depicts the longitude time diagrams of temperature fluctuations at 17 km subtropical region Cairo during March 2019 to February 2020. The maximum amplitude of KW in tropical region from Figure 4 (a - d) in spring, Summer, Autumn and Winter are 3 K, 4 K, 4 K and 4 K respectively. The periodicity of KW also observed in Spring, Summer, Autumn, and Winter are 8 days, 10 days, 11 days, and 12 days respectively. The temperature fluctuations from March 2019 to February 2020 at 17 km are characterized by the known climatological structure of warm temperatures over longitudes of 180° - 140° W to 50° W- 40° E in March 1- 10, 180° W- 180° E in August 15 - 31, 180° W- 180° E in September 1 - 25 and 40° - 180° E in December 5-25. The temperature fluctuation also from March 2019 to February 2020 at 17 km are characterized by the known climatological structure of cold temperature over longitudes of 40° W- 40° E in March 1 - 10, 0° W- 150° E in June 1 - 10, 40° W- 180° E in November 5 - 30 and 180° - 150° W in December 30 - January 25 and 100° - 150° E December 1 - 10 associated with maximum convection.

In Figure 5 (a - b) depicts the longitude time diagrams of temperature fluctuations at 17 km for tropical station Addis during March 2019 to February 2020. The maximum amplitude of KW in tropical region from Figure 5 (a - d) in spring, Summer, Autumn and Winter are 6 K, 4 K, 6 K and 5 K respectively. The periodicity of KW also observed in Spring, Summer, Autumn, and Winter are 13.3 days, 14 days, 11 days, and 12 days respectively. The temperature fluctuations from March 2019 to February 2020 at 17 km are characterized by the known climatological structure of cold temperatures over longitudes 50° W- 50° E in spring, 50° W- 100° E in summer, 100° - 40° W in Autumn and 100° - 40° W in winter. The temperature fluctuations from March 2019 to February 2020 at 17 km are characterized by the climatological structure of warm temperatures over the longitudes of 180° - 100° W in spring, 150° - 50° W in summer, 40° - 140° E in Autumn and 180° - 40° W in winter. The periodicity of KW in the warm and cold temperatures are 5 and 10 days in spring, 15 and 25 days in Summer, 10 and 10 days in Autumn, 10 and 20 days in Winter respectively.

Generally the maximum amplitude and periodicity at 17 km in subtropical region Cairo are 4 K (in summer, Autumn, and winter) and 12 days in Summer respectively, and also the maximum amplitude and periodicity at 17 km in tropical station Addis are 6 K (in Spring and autumn) and 14 days in Summer respectively. This is what we the expected result due to the KW temperature fluctuation maximum amplitude at the tropical region and its decay in the subtropical region.

Now we analyze the existance of KW in lower stratosphere and its periodicity of fluctuation at tropical and subtropical regions. The maximum amplitude of KW at 25 km in subtropical region Cairo is 2 K in spring, 2 K in Summer, 2 K in Autumn and 4 K in Winter. The maximum periodicity of KW at 25 km in subtropical region Cairo is 5 days in spring, 7 days in Summer, 8 days in Autumn and 5 days in Winter. In Figure 6 (a - d) depicts the longitude time diagrams of temperature fluctuations at 25 km subtropical station Cairo during march 2019 to February 2020. The temperature

fluctuations from March 2019 to February 2020 at 25 km are characterized by the known climatological structure of cold temperatures over longitudes $50^{\circ}W-180^{\circ}E$ in spring, $180^{\circ}W-100^{\circ}E$ in summer, $110^{\circ}-100^{\circ}W$ in Autumn and $180^{\circ}-60^{\circ}W$ in winter associated with maximum convection. The temperature fluctuations from March 2019 to February 2020 at 25 km are characterized by the climatological structure of warm temperatures over the longitudes of $40^{\circ}W-60^{\circ}E$ in spring, $50^{\circ}W-180^{\circ}E$ in summer, $50^{\circ}W-100^{\circ}E$ in Autumn and $50^{\circ}W-180^{\circ}E$ in winter.

In Figure 7 (a - d) depicts the longitude time diagrams of temperature fluctuations at 25 km tropical station Addis during march 2019 to February 2020. The maximum amplitude of KW at 25 km in tropical region Addis is 6 K in spring, 2 K in Summer, 7 K in Autumn and 4 K in Winter. The maximum periodicity of KW at 25 km in tropical region Addis is 8 days in spring, 7 days in Summer, 11 days in Autumn and 5 days in Winter. The temperature fluctuations from March 2019 to February 2020 at 25 km are characterized by the known climatological structure of cold temperatures over longitudes $10^{\circ}-90^{\circ}E$ in spring, $50^{\circ}W-100^{\circ}E$ in summer, $10^{\circ}W-50^{\circ}E$ in Autumn and $180^{\circ}-60^{\circ}W$ in winter associated with maximum convection. The temperature fluctuations from March 2019 to February 2020 at 25 km are characterized by the climatological structure of warm temperatures over the longitudes of $180^{\circ}W-180^{\circ}E$ in spring, $10^{\circ}W-150^{\circ}E$ in summer, $100^{\circ}W-10^{\circ}E$ in Autumn and $10^{\circ}-180^{\circ}E$ in winter.

Generally the maximum amplitude and periodicity at 25 km in subtropical region Cairo are 4 K in winter and 8 days in Autumn respectively, and also the maximum amplitude and periodicity at 25 km in tropical region Addis are 7 K in Autumn and 11 days in Autumn respectively, because of the KW temperature fluctuation's maximum amplitude in the tropical region and their decrease in the subtropical region at higher altitudes, which is anticipated outcome line with previous studies.

3.2. Altitude – Time investigation of kelvin wave in the TLS region

In order to study the vertical propagation of KWs, we constructed height - time variations of temperature kelvin wave fluctuations for tropical and subtropical stations during different seasons for March 2019 - February 2020 using RS and AIRS data. Figure 8 (a - d) shows Altitude - time variations of temperature fluctuations in subtropical station Cairo from RS data corresponding to (a) Spring (March 2019 - May 2019), (b) Summer (June 2019 - August 2019), (c) Autumn (September 2019 - November 2019), and (d) Winter (December 2019 - February 2020). The interesting feature from these figure is that KW phenomenon started below the tropopause height (around 12 km) and extends as high as 24 km and the vertical wavelengths are found 6 km during Spring, 7.8 km during Summer, 7.8 km during Autumn, and 10 km during Winter propagated with a period of 8.8 days in Spring, 7.8 days in Summer, 7.5 days in Autumn and 6.4 days in Winter. The vertical wavelengths observed here are in good agreement with those observed using high vertical resolution radiosonde measurements by (Holton et al., 2001; Ratnam et al., 2006; Kishore et al., 2005).

Figure 9 (a - d) depicts Altitude - time variations of temperature fluctuations in subtropical Cairo station from AIRS data corresponding to (a) Spring (March 2019 - May 2019), (b) Summer (June 2019 - August 2019), (c) Autumn (September 2019 - November 2019), and (d) Winter (December 2019 - February 2020). KW that propagated with a period of 13.3 day in Spring, 7.7 day in Summer, 13.3 day in Autumn, and 10 day in Winter with a vertical wave length of 9.2 km in spring, 11.2 km in summer, 7.7 km in Autumn, and 10 km in Winter.

In similar manner, height – time variations of temperature fluctuations in tropical Addis station were depicted in Figure 10 (a - d). It depicts Altitude - time variations of temperature fluctuations in tropical Addis station from RS data corresponding to (a) Spring (March 2019 - May 2019), (b) Summer (June 2019 - August 2019), (c) Autumn (September 2019 - November 2019), and (d) Winter (December 2019 - February 2020). KW that propagated with a period of 13.8 day in Spring, 14 day in Summer, 14.5 day in Autumn, and 14 day in Winter with a vertical wave length of 8.5 km in spring, 3.8 km in summer, 4 km in Autumn, and 4.4 km in Winter. The vertical wave lengths that we have determined here agree with previous studies by (Holton et al., 1995; Holton and Lindzen, 1968; Hirota, 1979; Ayoola et al., 2014; Sridharan et al., 2006; Tsai et al., 2004; Venkat Ratnam et al., 2006).

In Figure 11 (a - d) depicts Altitude - time variations of temperature fluctuations in tropical Addis station from AIRS data corresponding to (a) Spring (March 2019 - May 2019), (b) Summer (June 2019 - August 2019), (c) Autumn (September 2019 - November 2019), and (d) Winter (December 2019 - February 2020). KW that propagated with a period of 10 day in Spring, 9 day in Summer, 10 day in Autumn, and 9.2 day in Winter with a vertical wave length of 13.4 km in spring, 12.5 km in summer, 7.5 km in Autumn, and 11 km in Winter. The vertical wave lengths we observed here are consistent with earlier researches (Wheeler and Kiladis, 1999; Wheeler et al., 2000; Ryu et al., 2008).

Further, we proceed to verify the above observed KW periods and vertical wavelengths how much fit with theoretical vertical wavelengths derived from KW dispersion relation formulation mentioned in the methodology section 2.4.3. We calculated KW characteristics including wavenumbers (S), wave period (τ) in days, phase speed ($C_x = \frac{L_x}{\tau}$, where, L_x is the zonal wavelength for wavenumber 1 and 2, which is the circumference of the earth over the equator) and the vertical wavelength (L_z) observed during different seasons of March 2019 to February 2020 for tropical and subtropical station. Both observational and theoretical vertical wavelength's show higher coherence during most of the season's which greatly enhances the confidence in our observational methodology. As summarized by (Canziani et al., 1995; Schreiner et al., 2020), KWs are associated with three discrete temporal bands including slow (phase speeds of 20 - 40 ms^{-1} and vertical wavelength ~ 10 km), Fast (phase speed of 50 - 80 ms^{-1} and vertical wavelength ~ 20 km) and Ultra fast (phase speed of ~ 80 ms^{-1} and vertical wavelength ~ 40 km). Since the phase speed and vertical wavelength of KWs during different seasons. We can easily concluded that the observed waves belong to slow wave category except Summer and Winter tropical station Addis in AIRS data.

Table 1

Summary of kelvin wave characteristics in tropical Addis station

EKW parameter	AIRS				RS			
	spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
Wavenumbers (S)	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	1
Wave period (days)(τ)	10	9	10	9.2	13.8	14	14.5	14
Phase Speed (km per hr)(C_x)	167.5	186.1	83.8	182.1	121.4	59.8	57.8	119.6
Vertical wavelength (λ_z)(km)	13.4	12.5	7.5	11	8.5	3.8	4	4.4
Theoretical wavelength (λ_z)(km)	15.15	18.07	7.35	16.17	11.13	5.73	5.09	5.49

Table 2

Summary of kelvin wave characteristics in subtropical Cairo station

EKW parameter	AIRS				RS			
	spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
Wavenumbers (S)	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2
Wave period (days)(τ)	13.3	7.7	13.3	10	8.8	7.8	7.5	6.4
Phase Speed (km per hr)(C_x)	125.9	108.8	63	167.5	95.2	107.4	111.7	130.9
Vertical wavelength (λ_z)(km)	9.2	11.2	7.7	10	6	7.8	7.8	10
Theoretical wavelength (λ_z)(km)	11.53	10	5.5	14.59	8.84	9.88	9.78	11.14

Table 3

Summary of seasonal correlation coefficient of tropopause height fluctuation with kelvin and gravity waves

Atmospheric Wave	spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
Kelvin wave	0.72	0.86	0.81	0.74
Gravity Wave	0.12	0.48	-0.23	0.36

3.3. Effect of kelvin and gravity wave fluctuations on tropical tropopause variability

This section deals with kelvin and gravity waves association effect on cold point tropopause height (CPTH) variability using pearson correlation analysis. Figure 12 (a) shows the CPTH variability over tropical station using time series tropopause data from March 2019 – February 2020 using RS. It depicts interannual variability. The CPTH is vary from 14.19 to 18.55 km. The CPTH was seen to increase variation during March 12, March 15, June 15 - 17, October 11, October 13 and December 11 - 15. The tropopause height is strongly vary in April 29. These variation, as shown in Figure 12 (a), was an indicative of the presence of an atmospheric wave of kelvin and gravity waves. Temperature perturbations shown in Figure 12 (b) and (c) are direct reflections of the atmospheric gravity and kelvin waves. We observed from Figure 13 (b) and (c) the maximum kelvin and gravity waves are observed on April 8, Jun 13, August 30 and September 3 respectively, And also the minimum kelvin and gravity waves are seen on August 16, October 24, November 13 and July 29, December 29 respectively. The correlation of tropopause height with kelvin wave and gravity waves are 0.86 and 0.48 respectively. The maximum and minimum KWs are observed in summer and winter respectively. The maximum gravity waves are observed in summer.

We investigated the association between convection and KW activity using global OLR data as a proxy for deep convective activity, since transient deep convection is one of the main source mechanisms for the tropical Kelvin waves. The OLR data, averaged over (a) 22 - 35° and (b) 0 - 15° from March 2019 to February 2020, is displayed as a longitude-time graphic in Figure 13. Every day, the OLR data are made available in 2.5° x 2.5° latitude - longitude grid. To ensure comprehensive sampling, data gaps are filled by linear interpolation. Figure 13 clearly illustrates the very low OLR values in four regions: ~ 170 - 110° W, ~ 90 - 80° W, ~ 50 - 10° W, and ~ 90 - 110° E. These values frequently observe less than $270W m^{-2}$. Furthermore, Figure 13 indicates clearly the most intense and variable deep convection appears in the longitude range of ~ 0 - 50° E, with notable enhancements during the summer months of June through August 2019 in the Northern Hemisphere. A large portion of this variability is observed in features that propagate slowly eastward during this period. In addition, as previously mentioned, the climatological structure of the cold temperatures at 17 km in temperature fluctuations seen from July 1 to August 6 over within ~ 90W - 100° E longitude corresponds to convection activity (Randel and Wu, 2005; Highwood and Hoskins, 1998; Randel et al., 2003). Especially it is evident from Figure 13 (b) a low OLR values, in turn, are associated with significant convective activity during the summer, which may be the cause of the large amplitude kelvin wave amplitudes [Figure 12 (b)] and the strong correlation with the fluctuation of the tropical tropopause [Figure 12 (a)]. As suggested by (Shiotani and Horinouchi, 1993), the high correlation between Kelvin waves and background winds is most likely caused by thermal damping.

From the above observational results and previous studies, it is conceivable that the tropical convection generated over the Ethiopian region during the present observation period could be the plausible source mechanism for Kelvin waves (Wheeler and Kiladis, 1999; Salby and Garcia, 1987). Though Kelvin waves are seen in this study, their phase speed is substantially slower than that of moving OLR patterns Figure 13, indicating that the latter are not continuously related to convection. The observed Kelvin waves, on the other hand, are more in line with free modes driven by the wide range of convective variability, particularly over the active Ethiopian region.

4. Summary and Conclusion

This article examines temperature fluctuation in the upper troposphere to lower stratosphere (UTLS) region from March 2019 to February 2020, utilizing longitude - time and altitude - time data from RS and AIRS satellite data to study kelvin waves at tropical and subtropical regions. The seasonal kelvin waves indicate mixed waves with wave 1 and wave 2 components dominate for most of the time periods but individual wave 1 or wave 2 component only dominates in short time periods for about 7 - 15 days. It is found that the periodicity of observed kelvin wave is about 10 - 13.8 days in Spring, 9 - 14 days in Summer, 10 - 14.5 days in Autumn, and 9.2 - 14 days in Winter with a vertical wavelength of 8.5 - 10 km, 3.8 - 12.5 km, 4 - 7.5 km, and 4.4 - 11 km respectively in tropical Addis station. Similarly

the periodicity observed kelvin wave is about 8.8 - 13.3 days in Spring, 7.8 days in Summer, 7.5 - 13.3 days in Autumn, and 6.4 - 10 days in Winter with a vertical wavelength of 6 - 9.2 km, 7.8 - 11.2 km, 7.8 km, and 10 km respectively in subtropical Cairo station. A kelvin wave with downward propagation was observed in the time height cross section of temperature fluctuations from both RS and AIRS data. The height- time cross section of perturbation temperature from both RS and AIRS data showed downward propagation kelvin wave, which was more pronounced during Summer. The maximum amplitude of kelvin wave at the tropical station Addis is 8 K in Winter and for the subtropical station Cairo is level at 4 K in Winter, which supports exponentially decreases (decrement) of kelvin wave from the tropics to the subtropics. The CPT_h was seen to increase variation during March 12, March 15, June 15 - 17, October 11, October 13 and December 11 - 15. The maximum correlation of tropopause height with kelvin wave and gravity waves are 0.86 and 0.48 respectively. The cause of the large amplitude kelvin wave activity and its significant association with the tropical tropopause fluctuation may be below Outgoing longwave radiation (OLR) values, which are in turn linked to significant convective activity during the summer. Outgoing longwave radiation (OLR) data shows that deep convection activity is developed over tropical and subtropical region during the observational period EKW events observed in temperature fluctuations are either driven by convectively coupled wave or free waves over tropical and subtropical regions. Both kelvin and gravity waves were more prominent in the summer. Our results align with those of the earlier researchers.

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Figure 1: Temperature data (blue color) at 17 km from a - d in Addis station and e - h in Cairo station on 10 March 2019, 10 June 2019, 10 Sep 2019, and 10 December 2019, respectively, and red label for the sinusoidal fitting using AIRS data

Figure 2: Longitude - time diagrams of temperature fluctuations at latitude band of 22 - 35° N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter at 15 km in subtropical Cairo station.

Figure 3: Longitude - time diagrams of temperature fluctuations at latitude band of 0 - 15° N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter at 15 km in tropical Addis station.

Figure 4: Longitude - time diagrams of temperature fluctuations at latitude band of 22 - 35° N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter at 17 km in subtropical Cairo station.

Figure 5: Longitude - time diagrams of temperature fluctuations at latitude band of 0 - 15° N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter at 17 km in tropical Addis station.

Figure 6: Longitude - time diagrams of temperature fluctuations at latitude band of 22 - 35° N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter at 25 km in subtropical Cairo station.

Figure 7: Longitude - time diagrams of temperature fluctuations over 0-15° N during (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter at 25 km in tropical Addis station.

Figure 8: Altitude - time equatorial Kelvin wave signatures during different seasons from (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter in subtropical Cairo station in RS data.

Figure 9: Altitude - time equatorial Kelvin wave signatures during different seasons from (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter in sub-tropical Cairo station in AIRS data.

Figure 10: Altitude - time equatorial wave signatures during different seasons from (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Autumn 2020 in tropical Addis station in RS data.

Figure 11: Altitude - time equatorial wave signatures during different seasons from (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter in tropical Addis station in AIRS data.

Figure 12: (a), Daily cold point tropopause height (CPTTh) variation, (b) Kelvin wave fluctuation, and (c) Gravity wave fluctuation from March 2019 to February 2020 in RS data.

Figure 13: Outgoing long wave (OLR) data averaged between (a) 22 - 35° N and (b) 0 - 15° N from March 2019 to February 2020.

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At 15 km (100 hPa) in tropical region

At 17 km (70 hPa) in subtropical region

At 17 km (70 hPa) in tropical region

At 25 km (10 hPa) in tropical region

Outgoing Longwave Radiation in subtropical and tropical Station

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